

BRAZIL AND ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION: DISCOURSE AND POLICY FOR A NATIONAL SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

The debate on environmental security needs to consider the political and discursive dimensions. Supported by the general idea of protecting nature, it also includes protection of human beings, with the environment being an aggregating source of threat. In the political dimension, it is important to understand the existing structure of current environmental protection, in addition to investigating the relationships and interactions between different agencies. These agencies include security, defense, and preservation/conservation actors. With the predicted creation of a new force, in addition to the existing ones, the current idea of the structure needs to be rethought – will it be reworked or just added by something new? For our understanding to be broader, one should also study the discourses that run through environmental agents – if they are associated with a security reality, certain expectations can be created; if linked to environmental activism, other actors need to enter the discussion. This policy brief offers general reflections from which we can start to elaborate, academically and politically, issues related to nature.

BACKGROUND

In his first exclusive interview after assuming the presidency of the Republic, Luiz Inácio Lula da Silva brought up themes related to the role of the armed forces and the police in environmental conservation. Asked specifically about the protection of the Amazon, regarding borders, the head of the Brazilian State highlighted the interconnection between the action of federal and military agencies, especially in the field of public security, and the preservation of the climate.

Even more, he associated the fight against drug trafficking and the defense of borders with the care of biomes. According to him, “the climate issue, today, is a necessity to preserve the human species on the planet” (1). Lula promised stronger inspection, so that the forest could be “taken care of”. For this, it will be necessary to combine efforts from the Armed Forces, the Federal Police and a new force that will be created (2).

The president’s speech is filled with ideas of environmental security. This expression mobilizes two concepts – security and environment – that are not always understood in depth. The term “environmental security” ends up being treated in a combined way, according to a definition in which the environment is added as a security issue.

However, it should be noted that, sometimes, the environment is a referent to be protected – in which case it is associated, by some authors, with the concept of “ecological security” – and, in other

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situations, it is considered a source of threat to human beings – context best defined as one of, in fact, “environmental security” (3). There is also a third circumstance, in which environmental resources cause conflicts – known, by part of the literature, as an “environmental conflict” (4).

Thus, the very conceptual discussion on environmental security requires understanding what is being discussed. There are several nuances to be considered when talking about “environmental protection” or “preservation of nature” – and it requires an investigation into the language used. When we talk about “protection”, we are mobilizing a literature more associated with security and defense, related to the “politics of protection” (5). In the context of “preservation” or “conservation”, we bring environmentalists and natural science authors to the dialogue.

In this text, we explore the Brazilian situation, indicating that there are specific structures for each of the settings – one more associated with protection or defense; another related to preservation/conservation. In general, there is a national attempt to combine efforts – a fact that is especially relevant when we consider the inclusion, as of 2019, of the work of the Environmental Military Police in the National Environmental System.

Considering President Lula's speech about the creation of a new force – possibly subordinated to an independent Ministry of Public Security –, it is necessary that we try to better understand the structure of Brazilian environmental protection and preservation. The emergence of a new agency needs to consider everything that already exists, contemplating its future integration and activity.

FINDINGS

What I refer to as the “Brazilian system of environmental protection” is broad and complex. Several institutions and groups are part of it, from all power branches (the Executive, the Judiciary and the Legislative), especially concerned with the protection of the environment. Furthermore, we need to point out that these elements spread across all geographical levels: national and subnational; federal, state and municipal. It is still possible to think in transnational, regional, international and global terms; social, political, legal, economic and cultural manners; civil and military forces – in short, there are a series of classifications that can be made in order for this system to be better understood.

I emphasize the incorporation, in this system, both of military and police forces and of environmental agencies whose responsibility includes some need for inspection. At the level of the Executive branch, national and federal levels, three institutions stand out: the Armed Forces (the Army, the Navy and the Air Force), subordinated to the Ministry of Defense; the Federal Police, under the authority of the Ministry of Justice; and the Brazilian Institute for the Environment and Renewable Natural Resources (IBAMA), linked to the Ministry of the Environment. In addition, still in the Executive dimension, we have the action of subnational, state or municipal institutions – it is important to emphasize especially the role of the Environmental Military Police and the state, governmental institutes or secretaries for the environment.

Seeking to consolidate the action of all these entities, among many others, the National Environmental System (SISNAMA) was created in 1981, as a “set of public bodies (...), as well as non-governmental bodies instituted by the government responsible for environmental protection in Brazil” (6). The idea is that there is a national coordination aimed at harmonizing efforts, based on

the guidelines established by the National Environmental Policy (PNMA), published in the same year. Added to the structure of SISNAMA (7) there are protection mechanisms organized by the Armed Forces (military, national) and by the Police (Federal and Military, state).

Although IBAMA itself has what is called “police power”, so that it can control and supervise necessary activities, there is an entire security framework associated with environmental protection. Recently incorporated into SISNAMA, the Environmental Military Police, created in the context of each state of the federation, are important actors in the scenario we are dealing with – although their inclusion in the system is somehow contested (8).

Such police is a specialized unit that play a dual role: one as a public security police force, the other as an environmental security police force. They are at the forefront of combating illegal animal trafficking, illegal fishing and illegal timber trade. Its operations are essential not only in repressing environmental crimes, but also in preventing them. Although they are almost invisible to the public eye (9), the Environmental Military Police (PMA) assist the work of other important institutions, such as subnational environmental institutes. The work of the PMAs is portrayed by a recently published work, which highlights their origin, and brings important statistics on their activities (10).

Another police force that is part of this Brazilian system of environmental protection is the Federal Police (PF). Acting more closely with IBAMA, the “environmental PF” reprimands any crimes and offenses that pervade the topic of the environment. The main fight is against “organized environmental crime” (11), which intersects with other illegalities, such as slave labor and weapons/drugs/people trafficking (12) (13). This is the objective reality of the Amazonian territory, and these agencies also rely on the action of the Armed Forces to carry out their operations. Called “warriors of nature” (14), the federal police force that act on behalf of the environment receive specific training and need to be in close syntony with non-security environmental actors.

This entire environmental protection network needs to be understood and integrated, so that repetition or discontinuity of work can be avoided. More fundamentally: when thinking about the creation of a new force, as suggested by the president of Brazil, it is necessary to think in what context this will happen. And equally important: it is necessary to analyze discourses, in addition to policies, as they objectively guide the materiality of the political options presented.

CONCLUSIONS

Brazil is a state where the protection of nature goes hand in hand with security issues. Especially visible with the issue of the Amazon, the preservation of the environment requires thinking about what types of criminality are associated with the situation in which the environment is an object to be protected, and other human beings are the sources of threat. Joint action to combat these threats involves the action of several security agencies and military forces, together with environmental institutions that also have police power. Considering the discursive apparatus that justifies the securitization of the environment and understanding the acceptance of this panorama by society in general, it is necessary to investigate not only operations, but also the voices that speak for

environmental protection. Thus, it will be possible to contribute to the generation of knowledge and the elaboration of fairer and more effective policies.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- To deeply investigate the environmental security discourses that are elaborated by political authorities, to understand subjective dimensions related to the protection of nature. This understanding allows us to trace trends in planning and decisions, enabling the design of prospective scenarios that contribute to the protection of nature without, however, forgetting the human and humanitarian perspective associated with environmental crimes.
- To map in detail the entire current system and structure for nature protection, including: preservation and security agencies; federal, state and municipal entities; elements of the executive, legislative and judicial power branches; and international agreements and agency participation in joint operations with other countries.
- To elaborate an action plan that considers the intimate causes of the perpetrators of environmental crimes, seeking to understand their realities beyond mere inspection and combat. The understanding of the subjects who are discursively constructed as threats helps the joint and comprehensive action of other political and social sectors, mobilizing a continuous and effective prevention of crimes.

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